

Acknowledgement

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Chemical examination of seeds of *Amomum subulatum*

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AMOMUM subulatum (family Zingiberaceae).
Uses—Medicinal¹. *Previous work*—Ash contents of seeds². *Present work*—Powdered seeds were extracted with hot petroleum ether (40°–60°), then successively with cold methanolic hydrochloric acid (2%), ethylacetate and hot alcohol.

The petroleum ether extract gave viscous oil, hence was rejected. The 2% cold methanolic extract on column chromatography over silica gel followed by paper chromatography yielded compound A. The concentrated ethylacetate and ethanolic extracts both gave a creamish white deposit which on chromatography over silica gel yielded compound B along with few minor substances.

From a study of u.v. spectral data, degradation, m.p., m.m.p. the compound A, C₂₈H₃₃O₁₇, m.p. > 300° was identified as petunidin 3,5-diglucoside and the compound B, C₂₁H₂₄O₁₂, m.p. 230° (dec.) was identified as Leucocyanidin-3-O-β-D-glucopyranoside. Studies on minor substances are in progress.

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Lead-*n*-butyl thioglycolate complexes—A polarographic study

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IN this communication, composition and stability constants of Pb²⁺-*n*-butyl thioglycolate complexes have been investigated in 50% dimethyl formamide (D.M.F.) media polarographically. The values of ΔG, ΔH and ΔS are also reported.

Experimental

n-Butyl thioglycolate (referred herein as RSH) was supplied by Evan's Chemitics Inc., N.Y. and all other chemicals were AnalaR (B.D.H.). Freshly prepared solutions of the ligand and others were used to avoid the effect of ageing and air oxidation. NaClO₄ and Triton X-100 were used as supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor respectively. All solutions used for recording polarograms had in addition to RSH, a lead ion concentration of 1.00 mM, 0.1M NaClO₄ and 0.002% triton X-100 in 50% D.M.F. media. The entire study was carried out at a constant ionic strength μ = 0.1M NaClO₄ and at a pH 4.30 ± 0.04 maintained by adding 5.00 ml of Clark's and Lub's buffer of pH 4.2. The concentration of RSH varied from 0.004 to 0.012M.

A manual polarograph in conjunction with a thermostated H-cell was used for recording the polarograms against S.C.E. as a reference electrode in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen. The capillary had the following characteristics

$$m = 1.107 \text{ mg/sec.}, t = 4.85 \text{ sec. at } -0.3 \text{ Volt vs. S.C.E.}$$

Results and Discussion

The plot of i_d vs. $h^{1/2} t_{eff}$ yielded a straight line showing the diffusion controlled nature of the waves.

The plots of $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ vs. $E_{d.e.}$ were also linear whose

slopes (0.032 ± 0.002) were in agreement with the theoretical value for the two electron transfer process indicating the reversibility of the electrode reaction. The values of i_d and $-E_{1/2}$ for different ligand concentrations (C_X) are mentioned in Table 1.

The curvature obtained in the plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs. $-\log C_X$ (Fig. 1) showed the successive complex forma-

tion and hence the method of DeFord and Hume^{1,2} was adopted for deriving various functions $F_J(X)$. The intercept of a plot of $F_J(X)$ vs. (C_X) extrapolated to $(C_X) = 0$, is equal to $\beta_J X$. Fig. 2 represents the plot of $F_0(X)$ and $F_1(X)$; and Fig. 3 represents the plot of $F_2(X)$ and $F_3(X)$ vs. C_X at 27°. The plot of $F_3(X)$ showed a horizontal straight line signifying the formation of only three complexes represented as $Pb(S-CH_2COOC_4H_9)_n$ where $n = 1, 2$ and 3, whose stability constants were calculated at two temperatures viz., 27° and 37° and found to be

$$\beta_1 = 0.87 \times 10^2, \quad \beta_2 = 2.2 \times 10^3$$

$$\text{and } \beta_3 = 2.5 \times 10^5 \text{ at } 27^\circ$$

$$\beta_1 = 0.90 \times 10^2, \quad \beta_2 = 1.72 \times 10^3$$

$$\text{and } \beta_3 = 2.3 \times 10^5 \text{ at } 37^\circ.$$

TABLE 1. $-E_{1/2}$, i_d AND VALUES OF VARIOUS FUNCTIONS AT 27° AND 37°

Conc. of ligand Moles/litre	i_d (μA)		$-E_{1/2}$ (volts)		$F_0(X)$		$F_1(X) \times 10^{-2}$		$F_2(X) \times 10^{-3}$		$F_3(X) \times 10^{-5}$	
	27°	37°	27°	37°	27°	37°	27°	37°	27°	37°	27°	37°
0.000	7.4	7.8	0.395	0.395	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.004	7.2	7.5	0.399	0.399	1.401	1.403	1.00	1.00	3.31	2.68	2.78	2.40
0.006	7.1	7.4	0.401	0.401	1.658	1.652	1.09	1.08	3.66	3.11	2.44	2.30
0.008	7.0	7.3	0.403	0.403	1.963	1.945	1.20	1.18	4.17	3.51	2.46	2.23
0.010	7.0	7.2	0.405	0.405	2.348	2.291	1.34	1.29	4.78	3.91	2.58	2.18
0.012	6.9	7.0	0.407	0.407	2.821	2.736	1.51	1.44	5.39	4.55	2.66	2.35

tion and hence the method of DeFord and Hume^{1,2} was adopted for deriving various functions $F_J(X)$. The intercept of a plot of $F_J(X)$ vs. (C_X) extrapolated to $(C_X) = 0$, is equal to $\beta_J X$. Fig. 2 represents the plot of $F_0(X)$ and $F_1(X)$; and Fig. 3 represents the plot of $F_2(X)$ and $F_3(X)$ vs. C_X at 27°. The plot of $F_3(X)$ showed a horizontal straight line signifying the formation of only three complexes represented as $Pb(S-CH_2COOC_4H_9)_n$ where $n = 1, 2$ and 3, whose stability constants were calculated at two temperatures viz., 27° and 37° and found to be

Fig. 1. Plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs. $-\log C_X$

Fig. 2. Values of $F_0(X)$ and $F_1(X)$ for Pb^{2+} in *n*-butyl thioglycolate media at 27°. (○) $F_0(X)$; (—) $F_1(X)$.

The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have been determined using standard equations and are found to be

−4.39, 0.62 and 16.0 for 1 : 1 complex, −4.59, −4.49 and 0.32 for 1 : 2 complex and −7.61, −1.54 and 19.6 K.cal/mole, K.cal/mole and Cal/degree/mole respectively for 1 : 3 complex.

Fig. 3. Values of $F_2(X)$ and $F_3(X)$ for Pb^{2+} in *n*-butyl thioglycolate media at 27°.

(○) $F_2(X)$; (— — —) $F_3(X)$.

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A Study of Oxozirconium-1-nitroso-2-naphthol Complex and Colorimetric Estimation of Zirconium

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The potentialities of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol as a colorimetric reagent seem to be considerable in view of its colour reactions with many metals yet it has rarely been used as a colorimetric reagent. We report the results of our study of its use as a reagent for zirconium with which it is found to form a 1:1 complex.

The reagent, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (BDH), was recrystallised from methanol and water and a solution ($5.314 \times 10^{-4} M$) was obtained by dissolution of the solid in 50% ethanol-water. Oxozirconium chloride (Fluka) was recrystallised twice from conc. hydrochloric acid. The zirconium content was determined gravimetrically using oxine as a precipitant¹. A stock solution of the salt ($5.249 \times 10^{-4} M$) was used. Other chemicals were reagent grade. Twice distilled water was used for solutions. Measurement of

hydrogen ion concentrations was made with a Beckmann pH meter. Absorption measurements were made with a Hilger Spekker absorptiometer.

Absorptions were measured at 490 nm. The optical density was found to be a maximum in the pH range 2.5–3.5 and the pH of 3.5 was used for all measurements. Job's method² and the mole ratio method³ gave data (Table 1) which indicate a 1:1 complex. The molar extinction coefficient of the

TABLE 1. JOB'S METHOD AND MOLE RATIO METHOD

Zirconium(IV) solution ($5.249 \times 10^{-4} M$) (ml)	Reagent solution added ($5.314 \times 10^{-4} M$) (ml)	Absorbance of the complex (corrected readings)
Job's method		
1.0	9.0	0.034
2.0	8.0	0.059
3.0	7.0	0.064
4.0	6.0	0.087
4.5	5.5	0.094
5.0	5.0	0.106
6.0	4.0	0.098
7.0	3.0	0.090
8.0	2.0	0.070
9.0	1.0	0.040
Mole ratio method		
5.0	1.0	0.032
5.0	2.0	0.051
5.0	3.0	0.060
5.0	4.0	0.068
5.0	5.0	0.078
5.0	6.0	0.079
5.0	7.0	0.081
5.0	8.0	0.080

complex at this pH and 490 nm was 6.25×10^3 . Beer's law was obeyed in the range of 0–60 ppm of the metal ion. The method is not highly sensitive, the spectrophotometric sensitivity according to Sandell being $0.44 \mu g$ per cm^2 . The reagent is suitable for the analysis of micro quantities of zirconium where other methods fail or are not applicable. Interferences were studied by employing synthetic mixtures. Titanium(IV), aluminum, magnesium and calcium had no effect even when they were present in appreciable concentrations. Thorium(IV), uranium(VI), iron(III) and manganese(II) interfere as they also form soluble complexes under similar conditions. Anions like halides and nitrates do not interfere. Fluorides, phosphates and sulphates interfere seriously due to their complexing action on zirconium ions.

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